

Connecting international ecosystem restoration policies: a bird's-eye view

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Introduction

The RECONNECT project focuses on the social-ecological relations between protected areas and the larger landscapes in which they are embedded. It looks at the values, perceptions and narratives that underpin effective nature conservation.

RECONNECT explores in-depth the concept of boundaries through a series of studies in four selected cities spanning two continents. In these case studies, acknowledging existing boundaries allows researchers to show which obstacles exist and how they can be overcome to reconnect people with their surrounding natural environments. Ultimately, the goal is to provide insights for decision makers in how to reconcile competing land uses for the benefit of people and the planet.

One of the main questions that the project has explored surrounds the EU Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), which aims at restoring 20% of EU's land and seas by 2030. A key insight from RECONNECT is that for nature restoration to be successful, it needs to resonate with the richness of people's narratives. While they may vary – [our research identifies five different ones](#) – they all function as connectors, meaning that they can be shared by different groups and can represent the multiple interests of stakeholder groups in an inclusive way.

In increasingly polarised contexts, we are thus asked to find symbols that represent these narratives, joint reminders that the wellbeing of our natural environment goes hand in hand with that of people.

Which animal is then better placed to be the symbol of RECONNECT if not the extraordinary red-backed shrike (*Lanius collurio*). A migratory bird, smaller than twenty centimetres, that following the African-Eurasian Flyway System connects Africa with Europe.

Geographic range, *Lanius collurio*, BirdLife International and Handbook of the Birds of the World 2015. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2025-2

While classified as Least Concern in the [IUCN Red List of Endangered Species](#), the population of the red-backed shrike is experiencing significant declines, caused primarily by habitat loss and fragmentation.

Through its eyes, this policy brief looks at two key articles of the nature restoration regulation, namely the ones focused on agricultural landscapes and on urban environments. These targets have been chosen as they well represent the four case study sites in RECONNECT: Cape Town, Grenoble, Stockholm, Göttingen.

1. The EU Nature Restoration Regulation

Reducing fragmentation is intrinsically linked to the EU Nature Restoration Regulation. The legislation builds on the existing European Union’s environmental acquis, in particular the Birds and Habitats Directive. Yet it goes one step further and includes legally binding targets on specific ecosystems: wetlands, forests, grasslands, marine habitats, river and lakes, pollinators, heath and scrub, rocky habitats and dunes, agricultural landscapes, and urban ecosystems. The strength of the NRR lies in its comprehensive approach, underpinned by scientific evidence, and in its enormous potential in restoring the 81% of European habitats currently classified as in poor conditions.

After being approved following a polarised legislative process, the regulation – directly applicable to Member States – represents a win for both people, nature and the economy. In recognising this, national governments have already mobilised to implement the provisions of the law, albeit at different paces.

A potential beneficial factor in implementing the NRR at the national level could be a stronger mention of *diverse values* of nature - following the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF). In fact, one of the core considerations of the GBF, before delving into its four goals and 23 action targets, is the need for a recognition of different value systems:

Nature embodies different concepts for different people, including biodiversity, ecosystems, Mother Earth, and systems of life. Nature’s contributions to people also embody different concepts, such as ecosystem goods and services and nature’s gifts. Both nature and nature’s contributions to people are vital for human existence and good quality of life, including human well-being, living in harmony with nature, and living well in balance and harmony with Mother Earth. The Framework recognizes and considers these diverse value systems and concepts, including, for those countries that recognize them, rights of nature and rights of Mother Earth, as being an integral part of its successful implementation.

Photo by Elias Maurer on Unsplash

This framing is important not only in the development of nature strategies themselves, but also in their implementation phase. Communicating the benefits and aims of a policy document is nearly as important as the provisions contained in the document, especially if the targeted audience is broad and diverse.

A provision where the mention of diverse value systems and concepts could be included in the National Restoration Plans (NRPs) and linked to Article 14 of the NRR, where the preparation of such plans is outlined. The regulation requires Member States to *ensure that the preparation of the restoration plan is open, transparent, inclusive and effective and that the public, including all relevant stakeholders, is given early and effective opportunities to participate in its preparation*. Providing sufficient means and dialogue spaces for broad and meaningful participation is a way to support the inclusion of multiple values.

To go one step further, the NRPs implementation measures and monitoring could recognise how relevant diverse societal views on nature are for successful conservation – including values related to cultural and regional heritage, care and stewardship, learning, multifunctional and sustainable production, and collaboration. It would make apparent how diverse and plural the connections are between nature restoration, and people’s lives, experiences, activities, and emotions.

2. Identifying common symbols

Previous work from RECONNECT underscored how nature can be seen as a space for discovery, a collaborative space that bridges different interest groups' priorities, an area to protect, a generational responsibility, or a multifunctional production landscape.

Taking agricultural ecosystems as an example, we can see these divergences in view play out. For some, the land is seen as a landscape that provides goods for people and that supports the livelihood of farmers. Others might see it as an exceptional biodiversity haven and a space for learning. Those who have been caring for the land for generations might see it as intrinsic to their identity and cultural heritage. These multitudes are all true at the same time. Yet, polarising narratives have historically made it challenging for stakeholders to agree on how to protect of these ecosystems.

The [IPBES report on diverse values and valuation of nature \(2022\)](#) states clearly that the diversity of nature's values in policymaking can be advanced by considering a typology of nature's values that encompasses the richness of people's relationships with nature [...]. Diverse understandings of nature are expressed in different ways (e.g., via symbols, rituals, languages, and data and models)."

A successful implementation of the EU Nature Restoration Regulation will therefore be contingent on the ability of policymakers, experts, and stakeholders of highlighting shared values and finding common symbols. Here enters the red-back shrike, a symbol that can hardly be seen as dividing. Bird species conservation has always been a key pillar of nature conservation. For example, the Birds Directive is the oldest piece of environmental legislation in the EU and Birdlife International can be considered the first global environmental organisation to be established in 1922.

Choosing the red-back shrike as a symbol to communicate the importance of the NRR makes it also easier to relate technical and policy language. This bird weighing less than 40 grams travels thousands of kilometres during its life – a migration that transcends human borders and that inspires a sense of freedom and connection.

This species is also critical from a scientific perspective. It is amongst the species monitored for the NRR implementation in agricultural landscapes as part of the [common farmland bird index](#) and is present in the three RECONNECT case studies in Europe. Its population is stable, yet previous declines were mainly caused by the loss and fragmentation of habitat resulting from afforestation and agricultural intensification.

The NRR addresses exactly these issues that make life difficult for the shrike: while Article 11 focuses on restoration measures Member States should adopt to restore agricultural ecosystems, Article 14 highlights the necessity to map and address fragmentation. Seen the current trends in Europe on ecosystem connectivity, it is safe to assume that this threat would have increased in the future in the absence of the Nature Restoration Regulation.

Specifically, Article 11 obliges Member States to put in place restoration measures necessary to enhance biodiversity, achieve an increasing trend at national level on key selected indicators (grassland butterfly index, stock of organic carbon in cropland mineral soils, share of agricultural land with high-diversity landscape features), and to rewet peatlands. In doing so, it calls on the establishment of measures that ensure the recovery of common farmland birds, including the shrike, the NRR states:

Member States shall put in place restoration measures which shall aim to ensure that the common farmland bird index at national level based on the species specified in Annex V, indexed on September 2025 = 100, reaches the following levels:

- a) for Member States listed in Annex V with historically more depleted populations of farmland birds: 110 by 2030, 120 by 2040 and 130 by 2050;
- b) for Member States listed in Annex V with historically less depleted populations of farmland birds: 105 by 2030, 110 by 2040 and 115 by 2050.

The shrike thrives on restored, healthy, and connected agricultural landscapes. While it epitomizes the potential benefits of implementing the restoration regulation across European countries, it also points at the necessity to work together, across sectors of society, to achieve the common goal of nature-positive, sustainable agricultural landscapes. Looking at South Africa, the fourth case study for RECONNECT, the [latest national assessment](#) of the South African National Biodiversity Institute found that 34% of the country's endemic bird species are threatened with extinction. Similarly to the case in Europe, agriculture and land use change were cited as some of the main pressures.

Legal provisions, scientific data, and common symbols that represent shared values thus combine and foster meaningful collaboration across sectors of society. At the same time, projects like RECONNECT show the need to leverage the science-policy interface to continue creating these symbols across geographies with similar challenges.

3. Creating common spaces

For a bird like the shrike, spaces in between conserved areas are as important as the protected landscapes themselves - either on their migratory route, or in wintering habitats. RECONNECT focused specifically on these spaces and the multifunctionality of the landscape matrix that surrounds protected areas. A key dimension of the project was hereby urban ecosystems and on the gradient spanning from cities to protected areas, passing through peri-urban green spaces and agricultural ecosystems.

The Nature Restoration Regulation sets out clear targets for the restoration of urban ecosystems. Article 8 states that by 31 December 2030, Member States shall ensure that there is no net loss in the total national area of urban green space and of urban tree canopy cover. Furthermore, national governments must achieve an increasing trend in total urban green space area and in urban tree canopy.

In addition, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 – a flagship initiative of the European Green Deal – called on all cities above 20'000 inhabitants to develop ambitious Urban Greening Plans. The European Commission, to support these efforts, published a [guidance note](#) on these plans and launched an [online platform](#) where cities can access relevant information on how to best develop their strategies. With 75% of European citizens living in urban spaces, this combination of hard (NRR) and soft (EU Biodiversity Strategy) law instruments is essential in guaranteeing the well-being of the population and biodiversity conservation.

At the global level, these commitments and targets are reflected in the GBF Target 12 which deals with urban green spaces. Noteworthy to mention, in the target the global community agreed to *ensure biodiversity-inclusive urban planning, enhancing native biodiversity, ecological connectivity and integrity, and improving human health and well-being and connection to nature.*

Much like the need to find common symbols to overcome a polarised debate, the creation of collaboration spaces in cities within government authorities and within communities is a necessary step – especially as they can be often perceived as nature-deprived places.

[RECONNECT studies](#) showed that recognizing day to-day realities of local governance is key to ensure the effective implementation of biodiversity policies at the local level. The creation of place-based, inter-municipal learning spaces could foster respectful and effective knowledge exchange in urban settings.

Furthermore, tools like [geo-design](#) and [polycentric governance approaches](#) can support the uptake, ownership and implementation of biodiversity policies at the local level. To support these efforts, IUCN developed the [IUCN Urban Nature Indexes](#) with the aim to help policymakers, stakeholders and local communities in understanding the multidimensional impact of cities on nature, set SMART targets, inform planning, and monitor progress using science-based measures.

As mentioned above, the preparation of the NRPs must be transparent and inclusive, yet the participation of cities is often limited to discussing NRR Article 8. The creation of municipal-level groups for each of the NRR targets, financed by local authorities, could ensure wider uptake of the legislation. These groups can be composed of interested citizens selected through a citizen assembly model and led by experts within the administrative authorities.

Of particular importance would be to emphasise the connection between targets, for example by finding narratives to bridge the urban-rural divide. Through these collaborations policy implementation will be enhanced, conflicts reduced, and this will ultimately bring benefits to people and nature, including migrating species such as the shrike.

Recommendations

The Nature Restoration Regulation represents a lifeline to conserve and restore European nature. It is aligned with the Global Biodiversity Framework, and it is a testimony to the EU's global environmental leadership. Translating international policies to the local level requires community buy-in, and a governance approach that supports effective communication and learning between stakeholders.

With Member States preparing to submit their draft National Restoration Plans in September 2026, some insights from the RECONNECT project can support wider uptake of the targets amongst citizens, namely:

- Mirroring the considerations included in the preamble of the GBF, Member States should place an **emphasis on embedding different value systems in the National Restoration Plans**. An approach that is mindful of different worldviews is important in shaping new narratives supporting nature conservation.
- **All levels of government and civil society should strengthen their communication efforts on the benefits of nature restoration**. The message should be communicated clearly through a wide array of strategies, catered to the different target audiences. Here, common symbols, like the red-backed shrike, alongside successful case studies, can be a vector to overcome a polarised debate.
- **Urban and peri-urban spaces can be an extraordinary platform to move beyond a siloed approach to the implementation of the NRR**. The creation of municipal-level groups to discuss targets implementation could ensure alignment between communities and authorities, and a wider endorsement of the legislation. Tools like geo-design, spatial mapping, and best practices focused on polycentric governance models can be utilised to further empower civil society in the co-development of local strategies.

RECONNECT investigates the social-ecological relationships between protected areas and the larger landscapes that they are embedded in. The project explores ecological, social, and institutional connections to understand how protected areas relate to the 'outside' world. With this systemic take, the project goes beyond the conventional approach to biodiversity conservation and contributes to better coherence in discussions and decisions about the management of landscapes.

RECONNECT is 3-year long research project (2023-2026) sponsored by Biodiversa+ and the EU, with a budget of approximately 1,4 million Euros. It spans across four different case studies, namely Stockholm (Sweden), Göttingen (Germany), Grenoble (France), and Cape Town (South Africa). The partners are: Stockholm University, IUCN European Regional Office, French National Centre for Scientific Research, University of Helsinki, University of Göttingen, University of Western Cape and University of Cape Town.

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